

RARE EARTH ELEMENTS IN COASTAL SEDIMENTS OF THE NORTHERN GALICIAN SHELF: INFLUENCE OF GEOLOGICAL FEATURES

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Abstract. The Northern coast of Galicia, NW Iberian Peninsula, exhibits a variety of geological features: Ortegal allochthonous complex, Ollode-Sapo autochthonous domain and massifs of Bares, Barqueiro and San-Ciprian. In order to examine the influence of terrestrial lithologies on coastal sediments, 103 samples were collected in the Rias of Ortigueira, Barqueiro and Viveiro, their neighbouring shelf and the estuaries of Mera, Sor and Landro rivers. Aluminium, Fe, Sc, particulate inorganic and organic carbon and rare earth elements (REE) were determined in the <2 mm fraction. In addition, calcite, muscovite, quartz and riebeckite minerals were identified and quantified in 33 selected samples. The distributions of riebeckite and Fe reflect the influence of Ortegal complex on the coastal areas around the Cape Ortegal. The highest concentrations of ΣREE were found in fine sediments from confined inner parts of the Rias (up to $233 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$), while most of the sands contained $11\text{-}70 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$. ΣREE normalized to European Shale (ES) highlights the relative abundance of lanthanides ($\Sigma\text{REE}_N > 6$) near Cape Ortegal and the innermost ria zones. The ratio between light and heavy REE (L/H) showed lower values (4-11) around Cape Ortegal and the shelf while higher ratios (15-23) were detected in west of the Cape Estaca-de-Bares and in the inner Viveiro Ria due to elevated contributions of La and Ce. The L/H values normalized to ES reflects the importance of HREE in the adjacent area to Ortegal Complex ($L_N/H_N < 0.8$) and the LREE ($L_N/H_N > 1.4$) in the inner estuaries and west Cape Estaca-de-Bares. The highest REE individual ES normalised were measured in fine-grained sediments of the Mera and Sor estuaries. Sediments from the eastern shelf of Cape Ortegal presented enhanced ratios only for HREE. These results indicate that distribution of REE in the northern Galician region is highly depending on the neighbouring lithological pattern, contrasting with the situation found in the western Galician shelf and the Bay of Biscay. Lanthanides can, thus, provide a useful tool to follow the sediment pathway in the land-sea boundary zones, denoting continental geochemical imprint or fluvial outputs accordingly to the existing hydrological and geological conditions.

Keywords: lanthanide, sediment, estuary, ria, Galicia, NW Spain.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Rare earth elements (REE) have been used to trace natural processes in marine environment. Firstly, Haskin and Gehl (1962), Goldberg et al. (1963) and Wildeman and Haskin (1963) pointed out the interest of REE in early diagenetic researches in pelagic sediments. Later, Ronov et al. (1967) and Piper (1974) emphasized the role of REE to ascertain the sediment pathways. Biogeochemical cycling of REE has been studied in rivers, estuaries and continental shelves (Elderfield et al., 1990; Sholkovitz, 1993; and Ramesh, 1999; Nozaki et al., 2000). Rare earth elements have been reported as geochemical indicator related to anthropogenic activities (Olmez et al., 1991; Ridgway et al., 2003; Borrego et al., 2004). Lanthanides are used in industrial processes and consequently anomalous REE concentrations have been reported in terrestrial waters, and in river and marine sediments (Olmez et al., 1991; Protano and Riccobono, 2002; Borrego et al., 2004; Kulaksiz and Bau, 2007).

The advantage of REE applicability in marine geochemistry is their chemical fractionation and coherent behaviour during weathering (Dubinin, 2004; Leybourne and Johannesson, 2008). Lanthanides applicability ranged from studies of particle-water interactions in estuarine systems due to REE affinity to freshly formed iron and manganese hydroxides (Bayon et al., 2004; Marmolejo-Rodríguez et al., 2007), transport and provenance of sediments in coastal areas due to the low anthropogenic inputs to mitigate the natural sources (Vital et al., 1999; Munksgaard et al., 2003; Xu et al., 2009; Prego et al., 2009) and to geochemical processes in hydrothermal spots (Olivarez and Owen, 1989; Bortnikov et al., 2008).

Various works describe the lithological features and tectonic details of continental allochthonous complexes in the northwest of the Iberian Peninsula: Ortegá-Ordes, Malpica-Tuy, Brangança and Morais ophiolitic units (Ortega and Gil-Ibarguchi, 1990; Pin et al., 2002). Moreover, the terrestrial contribution of Miño River (Gouveia et al., 1993), Duero River (Araújo et al., 2002) and the Ria of Vigo (Prego et al., 2009; Caetano et al., 2009) to coastal mud patches has also been assessed. The REE composition of the weathering material from the Galiñeiro orthogneissic

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Complex has been determinant to trace the imprint of river-derived sediments (Prego et al., 2009). In the Bay of Biscay, REE was only tackled in order to identify the continental sources to the shelf sediments due to the Loire, Gironde and Adour load (Joanneau et al., 1998) and REE mobility in the deep sediments (Chaillou et al., 2006).

The northern Galicia region is composed by different continental geological domains, such as the allochthonous Ortegal Complex and the autochthonous of the Ollo-de-Sapo Domain. Their influence on coastal sediments has not been documented. In accordance with these geological features it may be hypothesised that the lanthanide distribution in sediments of that coastal region may differ depending on the land-sea boundary zone. Therefore, three objectives were set: (a) to establish baseline of REE data in river and coastal sediments from the Northern Galician, (b) to link the REE patterns in the coastal sediments with the geochemical characteristics of the landmass, and (c) to assess the continental source of lithogenic component in the sediments using the REE pattern as geochemical tracer.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. *The study area*

The northern coast of Galicia (7°30'–7°55'W; Figure 1) includes the Rias of Ortigueira, Barqueiro and Viveiro, designated as Northern Galician Rias according to the tectonic classification of Torre Enciso (1958). The surface areas of the Rias of Ortigueira, Barqueiro and Viveiro are 38, 10 and 27 km², respectively, considering the 30-m depth isobath as the ria-shelf boundary. These three rias are north or north-eastward oriented, mesotidal systems dominated by marine processes in from the inlets to the middle parts (Alvarez et al., 2010; Ospina-Alvarez et al., 2010). The inner parts are shallows (Evans and Prego, 2003), with extensive marshlands and well-developed beach barriers forming mouth complexes (Lorenzo et al., 2007). The Ria of Ortigueira, the western of the studied system, is an incised valley between Cape Ortegal and Cape Estaca-de-Bares. The main freshwater source is the Mera River with a fluvial basin covering 126

1 km² and annual average flow of 6.0 m³·s⁻¹. Eastern of Cape Estaca-de-Bares is located the Ria of
2 Barqueiro which receives as the main tributary the Sor River (202 km²; 15.2 m³·s⁻¹). The Ria of
3 Viveiro is located further East and receives in the inner most zone the Landro River (271 km²; 9.3
4 m³·s⁻¹). The annually discharge of suspended solids into the Bay of Biscay by Mera, Sor and Landro
5 rivers accounts only approximately 0.5% of total amount entering the Bay (Prego et al., 2008).
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11 The Northern Rias are located in a region with contrasting geological characteristics (Fig. 1).
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13 The Ortegal allochthonous complex, located at the west of the Ria of Ortigueira, exposes
14 abundant ultramafic rocks and metaigneous granulites, lower metamorphic facies with
15 abundant ultramafic rocks and metaigneous granulites, lower metamorphic facies with
16 pyroxenes, eclogites, amphibolite and serpentinites (Gil-Ibarguchi et al., 1990; Peucat et al.,
17 1990). The Ollo-de-Sapo autochthonous domain is characterized by metamorphic rock, mainly
18 gneisses (IGME, 1977; Aparicio et al, 1987). At the east margin of the Ria of Viveiro are the granitic
19 massifs of San-Ciprian (Capdevila, 1969), together with the Villalba Series (shale, sandstone and
20 gneiss). The surrounding area of the Ria of Barqueiro is mainly composed by granite, the
21 Barqueiro Massif, that is similar to the San-Ciprian and both rich in two-micas granite (IGME,
22 1977). In the southern boundary of Barqueiro Massif are present white quartz veins NWN-
23 oriented (quartz exploitation mine; Mirre, 1990). Moreover, in this ria it can found the Bares
24 Massif, a discordant, elongated intrusion of reduced dimensions (5 km²) made up of granodiorite,
25 and biotite (Ortega and Gil-Ibarguchi, 1990). Following this geological patterns the fluvial basin of
26 Mera displays metamorphic rocks mainly, with a lithology composed by gneiss and
27 metasediments, from the Ollo-de-Sapo Domain, shale, quartzite (Moeche Unit) and gneisses
28 bands (viz. Cariño with gneiss and eclogite), which form a part of the Ortegal Complex. The basins
29 of Baleo (53 km²) and Sor comprise mostly gneiss and schist (Ollo-de-Sapo Domain). The basin of
30 the Landro River covers a mixed area mainly makes up granitic rocks being part of the Manto-de-
31 Mondoñedo Domain (IGME, 1977).
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56 **2.2. Sediment sampling**

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One hundred and three samples of surface sediment were obtained in the three rias and adjoining continental shelf (Fig.1): 36 in Ortigueira, 29 in Barqueiro), 23 in Viveiro, and 15 offshore the rias). Sediments from the rias were sampled onboard the R/V *Lura* (July 2007), using small boats in the estuarine areas (July 2007) and onboard the R/V *Mytilus* in the adjacent coastal zone (May, 2008). A 30-L and 5-L Van Veen grabs and a Bouma type box corer (1.75 dm²) were used. In the intertidal areas sediments were sampled by hand. The uppermost sediment (0–1 cm) was collected with a plastic spatula, stored in pre-cleaned LDPE vials and kept at 4°C. Sediment samples were oven dried at 50 °C and the coarse fraction was separated by dry sieving through a 2 mm sieve (Retsch AS200). The <2 mm fraction was homogenised ground with an agate mortar and stored for further analysis.

2.3. Analytical Methodologies

2.3.1. Grain-size. Grain-size analyses were performed in the surface sediments collected in Northern Galician Rias and Shelf by dry sieving (Retsch AS-200). Sampled sediments were classified into mud, sand and gravel fractions, according to the Udden-Wentworth scale (Wentworth, 1922).

2.3.2. Carbon. Concentrations of particulate inorganic carbon (PIC) and particulate organic carbon (POC) were determined in duplicates of sediment samples in an EA1108 (Carlo Erba Instruments) elemental CNH analyzer at the University of A Coruña (SAI-UDC). POC concentration was measured directly, after removal of the carbonates by sample digestion with HCl at 80°C, and PIC concentration quantified by the difference between total carbon (TC) and POC concentrations.

2.3.3. Mineralogy. Muscovite, quartz, riebeckite and calcite minerals were identified and quantified in the crystalline fraction of the 33 selected sediment stations (Fig. 1). Analysis was carried out in the 'Jaume Almera' Institute (CSIC) following a standard procedure (Chung, 1974). X-ray diffractions of full samples were performed in ground samples using an automatic Siemens D-500 X-ray diffractometer in the following conditions: Cu ka, 40 kV, 30 mA, and graphite monochromator.

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2.3.4. Major and minor-elements. Approximately 100 mg of each sediment sample was completely digested with 6 cm³ of HF (40 %) and 1 cm³ of Aqua Regia (HCl-36%: HNO₃-60%; 3:1) in closed Teflon bombs at 100 °C for 1 h (Rantala and Loring, 1975). Subsequently, the bombs content was poured into volumetric flasks containing 5.6 g of boric acid and filled up with ultrapure Milli-Q water (Rantala and Loring, 1975). Metals were analyzed by flame atomic absorption spectrometry (FAAS) on a Perkin Elmer AA100 with a nitrous oxide-acetylene flame (Al) and air-acetylene flame (Fe). Iron and Al concentrations were determined with the standard additions method. The precision and accuracy of the analytical procedures was controlled through certified reference material analysis (AGV-1; USGS). The obtained concentrations (Table 1) were not statistically different from certified values (t-student; $\alpha=0.05$).

2.3.5. Rare Earth Elements (REE) and Sc. A different mineralization procedure was done for determination of REE and Sc. The first step was the above-mentioned digestion according to Rantala and Loring (1975), which was followed by evaporation and re-dissolution with 1 cm³ of double-distilled HNO₃ and 5 cm³ of ultra-pure water (18.2 M Ω cm), heated for 20 min at 75 °C and diluted to 50 mL with ultra-pure water. Moreover, two reagents blanks were prepared in the similar way for each batch of 20 samples. Concentrations of Sc, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er, Tm, Yb and Lu were determined by ICP-MS (Thermo Elemental, X-Series) equipped with a Peltier Impact bead spray chamber and a concentric Meinhard nebulizer. The experimental parameters were: forward power: 1400W; peak jumping mode; 150 sweeps per replicate; dwell time: 10 ms; dead time: 30 ns. The isotopes selected for the quantification of REE were either free from, or subject to minimum isobaric and polyatomic interferences (Smirnova et al., 2003). Polyatomic and isobaric interferences were minimized by setting the ratios ¹³⁷Ba⁺⁺/¹³⁷Ba and ¹⁴⁰Ce¹⁶O/¹⁴⁰Ce to 0.010 under routine operating conditions. Since the abundance of Ba, Ce and Pr in the samples was less than 700, 100 and 10 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ respectively, and the contribution of oxides relative to the analyzed ion plus the related measurement error was lower than 5%, the correction for estimates of ¹⁵³Eu and ¹⁵⁷Gd concentrations can be avoided (Smirnova et al., 2003).

1 A 7-points calibration within a range of 1 to 100 ppb was used to quantify element concentration,
2 using Indium as internal standard. A multi-element Quality Control (QC) solution was run every 10
3 samples. Coefficients of variation for metal counts (n=5) varied between 0.5 and 2%. Certified
4 reference material (AGV-1, USGS) was used to control the precision of the results. Levels of REE in
5 this material (Table 1) were not statistically different from certified concentrations (t-student;
6 $\alpha=0.05$). Reagent blanks always accounted for less than 1% of total concentrations in samples.
7 Differences for sediments zones at the Northern Galician Rias were validated using a Kruskal–
8 Wallis test followed by a Dunn post-hoc test.
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21 **3. RESULTS**

22 **3.1. Minerals**

23 Calcite, riebeckite, quartz and muscovite in the 33 selected samples exhibited contrasting
24 abundance distributions (Fig. 2). Riebeckite reached 19-20% of the identified minerals in the
25 sediments adjacent to the Cape Ortegal, while remained below 5% in samples near the Cape
26 Estaca-de-Bares. An opposite distribution pattern was encountered for quartz, since the most
27 abundant fraction (19-28%) was registered in those samples, and near the Cape Ortegal
28 concentration was below 5%. The abundance of muscovite in sediments varied from 40-50% in
29 the Ria of Viveiro, 20-30% close to the adjacent coastline, and less than 10% near the Cape
30 Ortegal. Sediment rich in calcite was observed off-rias, increasing its content towards the
31 continental slope (20-35%).
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47 **3.2. Grain size, carbon, aluminium, scandium and iron**

48 The grain size distribution of the collected samples revealed the predominance of sand in the
49 shelf (94±6%) and of fine-grained material in the innermost part of the rias and harbours (Fig.2).
50 The POC ranged from <1% in sandy sediments to 2-13% in the muddy sediments, while PIC varied
51 from 3-9% in the shelf to 2-3% in the rias (not shown). Exceptions were those muddy sediments
52 samples from the Rias of Barqueiro and Viveiro containing high quantities of shell debris (2-6%
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PIC) and sandy samples located around the Cape Ortegal (<2% PIC). The distribution of Al, Sc and Fe differed considerably (Fig. 2). Aluminium varied from 0.2% in coarser material to 6.6% in the muddy sediments, although sandy sediments nearby the Cape Estaca-de-Bares presented enhanced values (2.7-4.0%). Scandium concentrations ranged from 2 to 57 mg·kg⁻¹, being the highest values registered also near the same Cape (33-57 mg·kg⁻¹) and in the western of the Ria of Viveiro (33-37 mg·kg⁻¹). Iron concentrations varied from 0.3 to 6.0%, being higher in sediments near Cape Ortegal (5.0-6.0%) and lower near Cape Estaca-de-Bares (1.0-2.0%) and the Ria of Viveiro (0.3-1.7%).

3.3. Rare Earth Elements

The concentrations of total REE (Σ REE) in the all sediment samples ranged from 11 to 233 mg·kg⁻¹ (Fig.3). It accounted to total REE the La-Lu series of chemical elements, excluding the man-made element Pm. In general, muddy samples exhibited Σ REE up to 80 mg·kg⁻¹. Elevated levels were found in confined muddy inner areas: Celeiro harbour (111-233 mg·kg⁻¹), Ria of Ortigueira (75-132 mg·kg⁻¹) and Ria of Barqueiro (87-130 mg·kg⁻¹). Most of the analysed sands contained less than 70 mg·kg⁻¹. Relatively, high Σ REE values (40-60 mg·kg⁻¹) were also found in sands between the Cape Ortegal and the Bares massif as well as offshore San-Ciprian massif.

Sources of Lanthanide may be emphasized if their concentrations in sediment are normalized to a reference material and reported as a relative abundance plot (Coryell et al., 1963). In the current work individual REE were normalised to European Shale (ES). In this way, the abundance variation between REE of even and odd atomic numbers is eliminated and REE pattern of average shale should parallel the average upper continental crust (Haskin and Haskin, 1966). The sum of normalized REE (Σ REE_N) highlights the neighbouring shelf of Cape Ortegal and the innermost ria zones (Σ REE_N >6; Fig.3) as the most lanthanide enriched in reference to European Shale.

The distribution of the ratio (L/H) between light-REE (LREE), i.e. from La to Gd, and heavy-REE (HREE), i.e. from Tb to Lu, is not related to the sediment grain-size. The most noticeable aspect (map not shown) is the contrast between low L/H ratios in sediments around Cape Ortegal (4-6) in

1 comparison with the sediments of the shelf (8-11). Enhanced ratios were registered west of the
2 Cape Estaca-de-Bares (15-16) and the inner Viveiro Ria (up to 23) due to the high contributions of
3 La and Ce. The L/H normalization with ES (L_N/H_N), like before the Σ REE, is another advantage
4 perceiving any fractionation among the REE in the sediments due to no fractionation among REE
5 occurred in ES. Hence, the L_N/H_N (Fig.3) reflects the most importance of HREE in the adjacent area
6 to Ortegal Complex ($L_N/H_N < 0.8$) and the LREE ($L_N/H_N > 1.4$) in the inner estuaries and near the
7 coastal boundary between the Bares Massif and the Ollo-de-Sapo Domain in Cape Estaca-de-
8 Bares.

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19 The highest individual REE/ES ratios were registered in fine-grained sediments of the Mera
20 and Sor estuaries (Fig.4). These sediments presented higher ratios for lighter REE, and in particular
21 sediments from the Celeiro port. On the contrary, sediments from the western shelf of Cape
22 Ortegal and inner rias showed lower REE/ES ratios. Sediments from the eastern shelf of Cape
23 Ortegal presented higher ratios for heavier REE, in a clear opposition to the pattern observed for
24 Mera and Sor estuaries.

35 4. DISCUSSION

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38 This work illustrates how terrestrial geological formation may influence the coastal sediment
39 geochemistry. The north Galician coast is an emblematic example due to the uniqueness of Cape
40 Ortegal within the north-western Iberian Peninsula formations (Aparicio et al., 1987; Gil Ibarra
41 et al., 1990). The influence of the lithological characteristics on the coastal sediment composition
42 is manifested in various records. The enrichment of riebeckite and iron in sediments near the
43 Cape Ortegal is in line with the abundance of this mineral in the complex composed by mafic and
44 ultramafic rocks and the presence of other Fe-rich minerals (Mirre, 1990). These geochemical
45 distributions contrast with the high abundance of quartz in sediments of the Rias of Ortigueira
46 and Barqueiro and adjacent coastal sandy sediments. On the other hand, the massifs of San-
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Ciprian and Barqueiro made up of two-mica granite rich in muscovite (Capdevila, 1969; IGM, 1977) seem to influence the abundance of this mineral in coastal sediments.

Besides the sediment mineralogy, where calcite is the most likely reason for REE decrease in the shelf distant stations, as pointed out by Taylor and McLennan (1985) in similar areas, REE composition displays a particular significance as fingerprint of the neighbouring geological features. The low concentration of ΣREE and high values of ΣREE_N in sediments around Cape Ortegal shows undoubtedly the influence of the Ortegal Complex in the continental shelf (Fig.3). Two zones can be discerned around the Cape. The western sediments are under ultramafic rocks influence and display low ΣREE content and low L/H ratio. The low L/H and L_N/H_N ratios derived from LREE-depleted alloctonous eclogites of the Ortegal Complex (Bernard-Griffiths et al., 1985). The eastern end-Cape is slightly richer in ΣREE due to partial eclogites and basic granulites from Ortegal Complex, which is in line with the findings of Peucaut et al. (1990). These L/H ratios are below those found in the Ria of Vigo (Table 3), due to presence of LREE-enriched Galiñeiro orthogneissic Complex (Prego et al., 2009) and to the supply of HREE ($L_N/H_N < 0.8$, Fig.3; $(\text{La}/\text{Yt})_N \approx 0.3$, Table 3) from the Ortegal Complex. The increase of ΣREE concentration eastward the Cape Ortegal is in line with the sequence of the lithological features of the Bares Massif (granodiorites) – Barqueiro and San-Ciprian Massifs (granites) – Ollode-Sapo Domain (metamorphic). Nevertheless, their REE/ES values (Fig.4) are not distinguishable as result of the variability, except for some lanthanide elements of Bares Massif. This lack of discernibility may be partially influenced by a mixture of detrital weathering fractions derived from different land sources coupled with a removal of dissolved REE from the water. Planktonic uptakes, coprecipitation with iron hydroxides, and salt induced coagulation of colloids have been suggested as the removal mechanism (Nozaki, 2003). In the Northern Galician shelf REE pattern is more discernible than in the Loire and Gironde estuarine sediments where REE did not permit to discriminate between the possible continental sources (Joanneau et al., 1998). The sediments of northern Galician coast also show a deficit of REE compared with sediments of the west coast of

1 the Iberian Peninsula at Douro and Galicia mud patches (Joaunneau et al., 2002; Araújo et al.,
2 2007) and at east coast of the Cantabrian Sea at the American and Aquitania shelves (Joauneau et
3 al., 1998).
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7 In the innermost zones of the Rias of Ortigueira and Barqueiro and their fluvial end-members,
8 the sediment source is associated with metamorphic rocks from Olló-de-Sapo Domain (Sor and
9 Mera Basins) and Moeche Unit (Mera Basin). The sediments from these two estuarine systems
10 exhibited similar REE/ES patterns (Fig.4), where values were up to five times to those found in the
11 rias and shelf. This pattern indicates that fine grained sediments are richer in REE than sandy
12 sediments. For example, sandy sediments from the Landro estuary and the Ria of Viveiro, both
13 coming from the same granitic type massifs, have a similar REE fingerprint. Otherwise, fine
14 sediments from the Celeiro fishing port located in the inner of the Ria of Viveiro, display the
15 fingerprint of fine sediments from Mera and Sor estuaries. The exception was found for La and
16 redox-sensitive Ce that doubled the concentration in this area and it could be associated to
17 shipyard activities and mud sediments. Moreover, the positive anomaly of Gd normalized with ES
18 (Fig.4) observed in sediments of the above-mentioned three estuarine and dock areas may
19 presumably due to the lower stabilities of Gd complexes in seawater compared to those of their
20 respective neighbours in the REE series (Byne and Kim, 1990; Kim et al., 1991).
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40 Unlike the deficit of Σ REE in coastal sediments, values found in the Landro and Mera estuaries
41 were comparable with levels found in the inner sediments of the Ria of Vigo (Prego et al., 2009)
42 and Miño estuary (Gouveia et al., 1993; Alvarez-Iglesias et al., 2009). However, LHREE contents in
43 these two estuaries were lower ($L_N/H_N > 1.4$, Fig.3; $(La/Yb)_N \approx 1.0$, Table 3) than those found for the
44 inner Ria of Vigo and Miño estuary. The increase of REE content in fine particles of these
45 tributaries may be favoured by absorption-desorption processes during the estuarine mixing
46 (Sholkovitz and Szymczak, 2000; Nozaki et al., 2000; Yang et al., 2002; Marmolejo-Rodriguez et al.,
47 2007; Hannigan et al., 2010). Since fine grained particles are mainly settled in marshes and
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2 innermost parts, a minor contribution of REE fluvial end-members to the continental shelf can
3 thus be expected.
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6 7 **5. CONCLUSION** 8

9 The distribution of REE in the northern Galician coast is highly depending on the neighbouring
10 lithological pattern. The mafic and ultramafic rocks of the Ortegal Complex, as well as the
11 metamorphic rocks Ollo-de-Sapo autochthonous domain and the granitic massifs of San Ciprian
12 and Barqueiro, appears to determine the REE pattern in coastal sediments, where the Ortegal
13 Complex is the local source of HREE. This predominance also results from the low fluvial loads,
14 since fine particles with a different REE signature are accumulated in the innermost parts of the
15 Rias. These results point to the contrasting situation between northern and the western Galician
16 coast where fluvial discharges influence the Miño and Duero mud patches. A similar situation was
17 found in the shelf fine deposit zones in the Loire, Gironde and Adour plumes. Lanthanides can
18 thus provide a useful tool to follow the sediment pathway in the land-sea boundary zones
19 denoting continental geochemical imprint accordingly to the existing hydrological and geological
20 conditions.
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REFERENCES

- Alvarez, I., Ospina-Alvarez, N, deCastro, M., Varela, M., Gomez-Gesteira, M., Prego, R., 2010. Poleward intrusion in the northern Galician shelf. *Estuar. Coastal Shelf Sci.* 87, 545-552.
- Álvarez-Iglesias, P., Araújo, M.F., Gouveia, A., Drago, T., 2009. Geochemical analysis of Minho Estuary sedimentary record and its contribution to palaeoenvironmental evolution. *J. Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.* 281, 237-240.
- Aparicio, A., Sánchez Cela, V., Cacho, L.E., 1987. Petrological and geochemical considerations of the Cabo Ortegal Complex (NW Spain). *Rev. Real Acad. Cienc. Zaragoza* 42, 131-162.
- Araújo M.F., Jounneau J.M., Valério, P., Barbosa, T., Gouveia, A., Oliveira, A., Rodrigues A., Dias, J.M.A., 2002. Geochemical tracers of northern Portuguese estuarine sediments on the shelf. *Prog. Oceanogr.* 52, 277-297.
- Araújo, M.F., Corredeira, C., Gouveia, A., 2007. Distribution of rare elements in sediments of the Northwestern Iberian Continental Shelf. *J. Radioanal. Nucl. Chem.* 271, 255-260.
- Bayon, G., German, C.R., Burton, K.W., Nesbitt, R.W., Rogers, N., 2004. Sedimentary Fe–Mn oxy-hydroxides as paleoceanographic archives and the role of aeolian flux in regulating oceanic dissolved REE. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 224, 477-492.
- Bernard-Griffiths, J., Peucat, J., Cornichet, J., Iglesias Ponce de León, M., Gil-Ibarguchi, J.I., 1985. U-Pb, Nd Isotope and REE geochemistry in eclogites from the cabo Ortegal complex, Galicia, Spain: An example of REE immobility conserving MORB-like patterns during high-grade metamorphism. *Chem. Geol.* 52, 217-225.
- Borrego, J., López-González, N., Carro, B., Lozano-Soria, O., 2004. Origin of anomalies in light and middle REE in sediments of an estuary affected by phosphogypsum wastes (south-western Spain). *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 49, 1045-1053.
- Bortnikov, N.S., Gorelikova, N.V., Korostelev, P.G., Gonevchuk, V.G., 2008. Rare earth elements in tourmaline and chlorite from tin-bearing assemblages: Factors controlling fractionation of REE in hydrothermal systems. *Geol. Ore Deposits* 50, 445-461.
- Byne, R.H., Kim, K.-H., 1990. Rare Earth elements scavenging in seawater. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 54, 2645-2656.
- Caetano, M., Prego, R., Vale, C., dePablo, H., Marmolejo-Rodríguez, J., 2009. Evidence for early diagenesis of rare earth elements and metals in a transition sedimentary environment. *Mar. Chem.* 116, 36-46.
- Capdevila, R., 1969. Le métamorphisme régional progressif et les granites dans le segment hercynien de Galice nord-oriental (NW de l'Espagne). Ph. Thesis, University of Montpellier (France), 430 pp.
- Chaillou, G., Anschutz, P., Lavaux, G., Blanc, G., 2006. Rare earth elements in the modern sediments of the Biscay (France). *Mar. Chem.* 100, 39-52.
- Chung, F., 1974. Quantitative interpretation of X-ray diffraction patterns of mixtures: II. Adiabatic principles of X-ray diffraction analysis of mixtures. *J. Appl. Crystallog.* 7, 526-531.

- 1 Coryell, C.G., Chase, J.W., Winchester, J.W., 1963. A procedure for geochemical interpretation of terrestrial
2 rare-earth abundance patterns. *J. Geophys. Res.* 68, 559-566.
- 3 Dubinin, A.V., 2004. Geochemistry of rare earth elements in the ocean. *Lithol. Mineral Res.* 39, 289-307.
- 4 Elderfield, H., Upstillgoddard, R., Sholkovitz, E.R., 1990. The rare-earth elements in rivers, estuaries, and
5 coastal seas and their significance to the composition of ocean waters. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 54,
6 971-991.
- 7
8
9 Evans, G., Prego, R., 2003. Rias, estuaries and incised valleys: is a ria an estuary? *Mar. Geol.* 196, 171-175.
- 10
11 Gent, R., Menéndez Álvarez, M., García Iglesias, J., Tاراño Álvarez, J., 2005. Offshore occurrences of heavy-
12 mineral placers, Northwest Galicia, Spain. *Mar. Georesources Geotechnol.* 23, 39-59.
- 13
14 Gil-Ibarguchi, J.I., Mendia, M., Girardeau, J., Peucat, J.J., 1990. Petrology of eclogites and clinopyroxene-
15 garnet metabasites from the Cabo Ortegal Complex (northwestern Spain). *Lithos* 25, 133-162.
- 16
17 Goldberg, E.D., Koide, M., Schmitt, R., Smith, R., 1963. Rare-earth distributions in the marine environment. *J.*
18 *Geophys. Res.* 68: 4209-4217.
- 19
20 Gouveia, M.A., Araújo, M.F.D., Dias, J.M.A., 1993. Rare earth element distribution in sediments from the
21 Minho river and estuary (Portugal) – a preliminary study. *Chem. Geol.* 107, 379-383.
- 22
23 Hannigan, R., Dorval, E., Jones, C., 2010. The rare earth element chemistry of estuarine surface sediments in
24 the Chesapeake Bay. *Chem. Geol.* 272, 20-30.
- 25
26
27 Haskin, L.A., Gehl, M.A., 1962. The rare-earth distribution in sediments. *J. Geophys. Res.* 67: 2537-2541.
- 28
29 Haskin, M.A., Haskin L.A., 1966. Rare-earths in European shales: A redetermination. *Science* 154, 507-509.
- 30
31 IGME, 1977. Mapa geológico de España. Hoja de Cariño (1:50.000), Instituto Geológico Minero de España,
32 Madrid.
- 33
34 Joanneau, J.-M., Weber, O., Grousset, F.E., Thomas, B., 1998. Pb, Zn, Cs, Sc and rare earth elements as
35 tracers of the Loire and Gironde particles on the Biscay shelf (SW France). *Oceanol. Acta* 21, 233-241.
- 36
37 Joanneau, J.-M., Weber, O., Drago, T., Rodrigues, A., Oliveira, A., Dias, J.M.A., Garcia, C., Schmidt, S., Reyss,
38 J.L., 2002. Recent sedimentation and sedimentary budgets on the western Iberian shelf. *Prog. Oceanogr.*
39 52, 261-275.
- 40
41 Kim, K.-H., Byne, R.H., Lee, J.H., 1991. Gadolinium behavior in seawater: a molecular basis for gadolinium
42 anomalies. *Mar. Chem.* 36, 107-120.
- 43
44
45 Leybourne, M., Johannesson, K., 2008. Rare earth elements (REE) and yttrium in stream waters, stream
46 sediments, and Fe–Mn oxyhydroxides: Fractionation, speciation, and controls over REE + Y patterns in
47 the surface environment. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 72, 5962-5983.
- 48
49
50 Lorenzo, F., Alonso, A., Pagés, J.L., 2007. Erosion and accretion of beach and spit systems in northwest
51 Spain: A response to human activity. *J. Coast. Res.* 23, 834-845.
- 52
53 Kulaksız, S., Bau, M., 2007. Contrasting behaviour of anthropogenic gadolinium and natural rare earth
54 elements in estuaries and the gadolinium input into the North Sea. *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 260, 361-371.
- 55
56 Marmolejo-Rodríguez, A.J., Prego, R., Meyer-Willerer, A., Shumilin, E., Sapozhnikov, D., 2007. Rare earth
57 elements in iron oxy-hydroxide rich sediments from the Marabasco River-Estuary system (Pacific coast
58 of Mexico). REE affinity with iron and aluminium. *J. Geochem. Explor.* 94, 43-51.
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62
63
64
65
- Mirre, J.C., 1990. Guia dos minerais de Galicia, Editorial Galaxia, Vigo.
- Munksgaard, N.C., Lim, Kezia, Parry, D.L., 2003. Rare earth elements as provenance indicators in North Australian estuarine and coastal marine sediments. *Est., Coastal Shelf Sci.* 57, 399-409.
- Nozaki, Y., Lerche, D., Alibo, D.S., Snidvongs, A., 2000. The estuarine geochemistry of rare earth elements and indium in the Chao Phraya River, Thailand. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 64, 3983-3994.
- Nozaki, Y., 2003. Rare Earth elements and their isotopes in the ocean. In: Steele, J.H., Thorpe, S.A., Turekian, K.K. (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Ocean Sciences*. Academic Press, San Diego, pp. 2354-2366.
- Olivarez, A.M., Owen, R.M., 1989. REE/Fe variations in hidrothermal sediments: implications for the REE content of seawater. *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 53, 757-762.
- Olmez, I., Sholkovitz, E.R., Hermann, D., Eganhouse, R.P., 1991. Rare earth element geochemistry of southern California: a new anthropogenic indicator. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 25, 310-316.
- Ortega, L.A., Gil-Ibarguchi, J.I., 1990. The genesis of Late Hercynian granitoids from Galicia (northwestern Spain): inferences from REE studies. *J. Geol.* 98, 189-211.
- Ospina-Alvarez, N., Prego, R., Álvarez, I., deCastro, M., Álvarez-Ossorio, M.T., Pazos, Y., Campos, M.J., Bernárdez, P., Gómez-Gesteira, M., Varela, M., 2010. Oceanographical patterns during an upwelling-downwelling event in the northern Galician Rias. Comparison with the whole ria system (NW of Iberian Peninsula). *Cont. Shelf Res.* 30, 1362-1372.
- Peucat, J.J., Bernard-Griffiths, J., Dallmeyer, R.D., Menot, P., Cornichet, J., Iglesias Ponce de Leon, M., Gil-Ibarguchi, J.I., 1990. Geochemical and geochronological cross-section of the deep Hercynian crust: the Cabo Ortegal high-pressure nappes (NW Spain). *Tectonophysics* 177, 263-292.
- Pin, C., Paquete, J.L., Santos-Zalduegui, J. F., Gil-Ibarguchi, J.I., 2002. Early Devonian suprasubduction-zone ophiolite related to incipient collisional processes in the Western Variscan Belt: the Sierra de Careón Unit, Ordenes Complex, Galicia. *Geol. Soc. Am. Bull.* 364, 57-71.
- Piper, D.Z., 1974. Rare earth elements in the sedimentary cycle: a summary. *Chem. Geol.* 14, 285-304.
- Prego, R., Boi, P., Cobelo-García, A., 2008. The contribution of total suspended solids to the Bay of Biscay by Cantabrian Rivers (northern coast of the Iberian Peninsula). *J. Marine Syst.* 72, 342-349.
- Prego, R., Marmolejo, J., Caetano, M. Vale, C., 2009. Rare earth elements in sediments of the Vigo Ria (NW Iberian Peninsula). *Cont. Shelf Res.* 29, 896-902.
- Protano, G., Riccobono, F., 2002. High contents of rare earth elements (REEs) in stream waters of a Cu-Pb-Zn mining area. *Environ. Pollut.* 117, 499-514.
- Ramesh R., Ramanathan A.L., James R.A., Subramanian V., Jacobsen S.B., Holland H.D., 1999. Rare earth elements and heavy metal distribution in estuarine sediments of east coast of India. *Hydrobiologia* 397, 89-99.
- Rantala R., Loring, D., 1975. Multi-element analysis of silicate rocks and marine sediments by atomic absorption spectrophotometry. *Atomic Absorption Newsletter* 14, 117-120.
- Ridgway J., Breward N., Langston W.J., Lister R., Rees J.G. Rowlett, S.M., 2003. Distinguishing between natural and anthropogenic sources of metals entering the Irish Sea. *Appl. Geochem.* 18, 283-309.

- 1 Ronov, A.B., Balashov, Y.A., Migdisov, A.A., 1967. Geochemistry of the rare earths in the sedimentary cycle.
2 Geochem. Int. 4, 1-17.
- 3 Sholkovitz, E.R., 1993. The geochemistry of rare earth elements in the Amazon River estuary. Geochim.
4 Cosmochim. Acta 57, 2181-2190.
- 5
6 Sholkovitz, E., Szymczak R., 2000. The estuarine chemistry of rare earth elements: comparison of the
7 Amazon, Fly, Sepik and the Gulf of Papua Systems. Earth Planet. Sci. Lett. 179, 299-309.
- 8
9 Smirnova, E.V., Fedorova, I.N., Sandimirova, G.P., Petrov, L.L., Balbekina, N.G., Lozhkin, V.I., 2003.
10 Determination of rare earth elements in black shales by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry.
11 Spectrochim. Acta B: Atomic Spectroscopy 58, 329-340.
- 12
13 Taylor, S.R., McLennan, S.M., 1985. The Continental Crust: Its Composition and Evolution. Blackwell, Oxford.
- 14
15 Torre-Enciso, E., 1958. Estado actual del conocimiento de las rias gallegas, in: Homenaxe a X.R. Otero
16 Pedrayo, Editorial Galaxia, Vigo, pp. 237-250.
- 17
18 Vital, H., Stattegger, K., Garbe-Schonberg, C.D., 1999. Composition and trace-element geochemistry of
19 detrital clay and heavy-mineral suites of the lowermost Amazon River: a provenance study. J. Sediment.
20 Res. A 69, 563-575.
- 21
22 Wentworth, C.K., 1922. A scale of grade and class terms for clastic sediments. J. Geol. 30, 377-392.
- 23
24 Wildeman, T.R., Haskin, L.A., 1963. Rare earth elements in ocean sediments. J. Geophys. Res. 70, 2903-
25 2910.
- 26
27 Yang, S.Y., Jung, H.S., Choi, M.S., Li, C.X., 2002. The rare earth element compositions of the Changjiang
28 (Yangtze) and Huanghe (Yellow) river sediments. Earth Planet. Sci. Lett. 201, 407-419.
- 29
30 Xu, Z., Lim, D., Choi, J., Yang, S., Jung, H., 2009. Rare earth elements in bottom sediments of major rivers
31 around the Yellow Sea: implications for sediment provenance. Geo-Marine Lett. 29, 291-300.
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40 **Figure Captions**

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42 Figure 1. Detailed sketch map showing the main geological units and the lithological
43 characteristics of the northern coast of Galicia. Dots indicate the position of the surface
44 sediment sampling. White dots specify the samples where mineralogical analyses were
45 conducted. Lithology map was available from the Spatial Data Infrastructure of Galicia
46 <http://sitga.xunta.es/sitganet/index.aspx?lang=gl>
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54 Figure 2. Distribution of relevant minerals and metals in surface sediments associated to the main
55 lithological characteristics of the northern coast of Galicia.
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Figure 3. Distribution of rare earth elements, without (ΣREE) and with (ΣREE_N) ES normalization and its REE light-heavy normalized relationship (L_N/H_N) in surface sediments of the Northern Galician Rias and their neighbouring shelf.

Figure 4. Patterns of REE fingerprints, normalized to European Shale, of the surface sediments of the Northern Galician Rias and their neighbouring shelf.

Table 1. Measured average concentrations and standard deviations of Al (%), Fe (%) and Sc, Y and REE ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$) in AGV-1 from the United States Geological Survey.

AGV-1	Al	Fe	Sc	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er	Tm	Yb	Lu
measured	8.5±0.2	4.7±0.3	13±2	39±4	62±3	7.7±0.5	30±2	5.5±0.3	1.8±0.1	6.0±0.4	0.7±0.1	3.6±0.1	0.68±0.02	1.83±0.17	0.25±0.01	1.6±0.1	0.25±0.02
certified	8.7±0.2	4.8±0.4	12 ±1	41±2	67±6	7.6*	33±3	5.9±0.4	1.6±0.1	5.0±0.6	0.7±0.1	3.6±0.4	0.72±0.14	1.88±0.04	0.27±0.01	1.7±0.2	0.25±0.03

*informative value

Table 2. Concentration of rare earth elements (REE) measured in superficial sediment of the Northern Galician Ras and its neighbouring continental shelf. REE units are in mg·kg⁻¹ while Al and Fe in %.

UTM coordinates		Al	Fe	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Eu	Gd	Tb	Dy	Ho	Er	Tm	Yb	Lu
Lat. (N)	Long. (W)																
4834697	612332	5.8	0.9	4.0	7.9	0.9	3.4	0.7	0.28	2.7	0.10	0.56	0.11	0.31	0.05	0.32	0.05
4835262	612887	4.3	0.7	9.2	26.3	3.1	11.6	2.4	0.50	2.5	0.30	1.51	0.26	0.70	0.09	0.58	0.09
4837259	612692	6.0	3.5	34.5	88.7	6.9	26.7	5.2	1.17	5.7	0.67	3.59	0.66	1.88	0.25	1.66	0.25
4836923	612536	5.6	2.7	19.1	55.4	6.5	24.8	4.8	1.07	5.3	0.62	3.20	0.58	1.65	0.21	1.39	0.21
4836269	613273	4.2	0.9	8.0	22.6	2.6	9.7	1.9	0.54	2.1	0.25	1.32	0.24	0.69	0.09	0.60	0.09
4835711	613121	3.2	0.7	4.5	12.5	1.5	5.3	1.0	0.37	1.1	0.12	0.63	0.11	0.32	0.04	0.30	0.05
4835708	612960	6.9	2.8	34.3	54.7	6.6	25.1	4.8	1.16	5.4	0.64	3.37	0.62	1.72	0.22	1.46	0.21
4834811	612491	5.0	2.2	17.9	50.5	5.8	22.0	4.1	0.86	4.3	0.46	2.21	0.38	1.03	0.13	0.90	0.13
4833809	612346	4.9	1.7	8.0	22.1	2.6	9.7	1.8	0.51	2.1	0.25	1.34	0.26	0.78	0.11	0.81	0.12
4833581	612028	4.2	0.7	5.9	16.1	1.9	6.9	1.3	0.39	1.5	0.17	0.87	0.15	0.42	0.05	0.36	0.05
4832697	612284	3.9	0.8	5.9	16.0	1.9	7.1	1.4	0.43	1.5	0.18	0.95	0.17	0.48	0.06	0.45	0.07
4836048	613357	6.2	2.8	47.2	118.1	9.1	34.3	6.6	1.30	6.6	0.78	3.98	0.71	1.95	0.27	1.77	0.26
4837373	612851	5.8	3.5	32.3	85.2	6.5	25.3	4.9	1.12	5.4	0.63	3.36	0.62	1.76	0.24	1.58	0.24
4837587	612364	2.1	1.4	8.0	26.8	3.0	11.7	2.5	0.59	2.8	0.37	2.13	0.41	1.20	0.15	0.99	0.14
4839713	613295	0.3	0.6	1.9	4.8	0.6	2.7	0.6	0.19	0.8	0.10	0.59	0.12	0.34	0.04	0.25	0.04
4840263	612963	3.8	2.3	8.9	25.7	3.2	12.8	2.7	0.69	3.1	0.41	2.33	0.45	1.31	0.18	1.18	0.17
4842493	613409	1.8	1.6	5.5	20.1	2.0	8.3	1.8	0.54	2.3	0.31	1.83	0.36	1.05	0.14	0.89	0.13
4845055	613849	2.7	1.4	4.5	9.4	1.3	5.2	1.2	0.34	1.4	0.23	1.32	0.27	0.77	0.11	0.69	0.10
4848375	612995	4.3	1.3	7.2	15.6	1.8	7.1	1.5	0.43	1.7	0.25	1.46	0.29	0.86	0.12	0.82	0.12
4841492	613346	2.9	1.8	7.1	20.4	2.6	10.3	2.2	0.63	2.6	0.34	1.97	0.38	1.10	0.14	0.92	0.13
4843005	610822	2.8	1.0	7.7	24.8	2.8	10.8	2.3	0.55	2.7	0.35	1.94	0.36	1.00	0.12	0.75	0.10
4845468	611989	1.7	0.7	3.1	8.8	1.1	4.3	0.9	0.27	1.1	0.14	0.80	0.15	0.44	0.06	0.37	0.05
4842305	615427	2.5	1.7	6.1	17.7	2.2	9.0	1.9	0.59	2.4	0.32	1.88	0.37	1.07	0.14	0.90	0.13
4840904	604572	4.8	2.2	14.0	35.9	4.7	18.0	3.5	0.83	3.8	0.46	2.44	0.45	1.28	0.17	1.09	0.16
4841466	604966	5.3	0.9	9.8	15.7	2.1	8.2	1.6	0.53	1.8	0.23	1.22	0.24	0.70	0.10	0.62	0.09
4843029	605505	3.1	1.2	7.6	17.1	2.4	9.4	1.8	0.58	2.0	0.24	1.32	0.25	0.71	0.09	0.60	0.09
4844032	605650	2.4	0.6	2.0	5.1	0.7	2.6	0.5	0.18	0.6	0.07	0.36	0.07	0.19	0.02	0.16	0.02
4844037	605972	2.9	1.6	8.0	19.5	2.7	10.6	2.1	0.62	2.5	0.32	1.78	0.34	0.97	0.12	0.77	0.11
4843601	606543	4.9	2.6	13.1	33.6	4.4	17.5	3.5	0.84	4.0	0.49	2.66	0.50	1.44	0.19	1.26	0.19
4842795	604703	3.0	0.4	5.2	11.4	1.6	6.0	1.1	0.46	1.3	0.16	0.87	0.16	0.46	0.06	0.39	0.06
4842021	604957	3.0	0.9	6.1	13.8	1.9	7.5	1.4	0.50	1.6	0.19	1.06	0.20	0.56	0.07	0.47	0.07
4845025	605232	3.3	1.2	8.4	20.3	2.7	10.1	1.9	0.61	2.1	0.24	1.27	0.24	0.68	0.08	0.57	0.08
4840472	605384	6.6	3.6	16.9	43.6	5.7	22.2	4.4	1.07	5.1	0.64	3.52	0.67	1.91	0.25	1.64	0.25
4839579	605076	5.8	3.4	21.4	52.5	7.1	27.1	5.3	1.21	6.1	0.73	3.92	0.73	2.04	0.25	1.60	0.23
4840673	604011	4.0	2.9	22.0	50.7	7.0	26.5	5.1	1.13	6.2	0.75	3.98	0.75	2.07	0.24	1.53	0.22
4840233	604260	5.6	2.9	18.3	45.8	6.1	23.7	4.8	1.09	5.5	0.68	3.62	0.68	1.89	0.23	1.53	0.23
4839786	604105	3.7	1.7	17.3	55.4	4.8	19.0	3.8	0.78	3.9	0.43	2.22	0.42	1.19	0.15	1.00	0.16
4844150	606132	4.0	1.2	9.1	15.6	2.2	8.4	1.6	0.45	1.7	0.24	1.27	0.25	0.70	0.09	0.60	0.09
4845590	605867	2.1	1.6	8.1	15.6	1.9	7.5	1.6	0.48	1.9	0.23	1.31	0.25	0.72	0.10	0.64	0.10
4845838	607474	1.5	2.1	11.3	21.8	2.7	10.4	2.2	0.58	2.6	0.31	1.70	0.32	0.93	0.13	0.81	0.13
4846970	608744	2.8	2.1	5.8	16.6	2.1	8.7	1.9	0.56	2.3	0.30	1.80	0.36	1.09	0.16	1.08	0.16
4848435	610008	2.7	1.4	3.5	6.7	0.9	3.8	0.9	0.27	1.8	0.15	0.88	0.18	0.53	0.07	0.47	0.07
4845291	607966	2.4	2.2	6.2	17.6	2.2	9.0	1.9	0.55	2.3	0.30	1.69	0.33	0.94	0.13	0.83	0.12
4845147	605955	2.5	2.4	15.2	30.2	3.6	14.0	2.9	0.68	3.2	0.37	2.03	0.39	1.10	0.16	0.99	0.15
4845045	606520	2.9	2.0	8.7	23.9	3.0	11.9	2.4	0.64	2.8	0.34	1.89	0.36	1.03	0.14	0.90	0.13
4846744	608506	3.1	2.1	6.8	18.8	2.4	9.5	2.0	0.59	2.8	0.30	1.73	0.34	0.97	0.13	0.85	0.13
4846046	606585	2.3	1.2	7.5	14.5	1.8	7.3	1.7	0.52	1.8	0.21	1.19	0.23	0.68	0.10	0.62	0.10
4846841	607619	3.1	1.3	4.9	12.2	1.6	6.3	1.3	0.49	1.6	0.20	1.13	0.22	0.65	0.09	0.59	0.09
4844959	608052	3.3	1.9	7.1	19.6	2.4	9.7	2.1	0.54	2.4	0.30	1.67	0.32	0.91	0.12	0.79	0.11
4845966	608518	0.7	0.5	3.3	6.1	0.8	3.1	0.7	0.19	0.8	0.10	0.59	0.11	0.33	0.05	0.28	0.04
4846986	609710	3.3	2.1	7.0	19.9	2.4	9.6	2.0	0.55	2.2	0.27	1.50	0.29	0.83	0.11	0.73	0.11
4847400	607851	3.0	0.7	4.9	12.8	1.5	6.0	1.2	0.52	1.5	0.19	1.09	0.22	0.64	0.09	0.59	0.09
4837262	591003	1.1	2.7	3.2	8.9	1.2	4.9	1.0	0.32	1.2	0.16	0.90	0.18	0.52	0.07	0.46	0.07
4840040	591126	1.0	2.7	2.8	7.6	1.1	4.5	1.0	0.32	1.2	0.16	0.97	0.19	0.56	0.07	0.48	0.07
4840040	591126	1.2	1.6	1.9	3.6	0.5	2.3	0.5	0.17	0.6	0.09	0.54	0.11	0.32	0.04	0.25	0.04
4838669	596304	5.4	4.4	20.9	53.9	7.0	27.1	5.3	1.31	6.1	0.75	4.13	0.80	2.30	0.30	1.99	0.30
4839425	594762	1.4	3.6	2.6	7.2	1.0	4.4	1.0	0.35	1.3	0.19	1.15	0.23	0.68	0.09	0.61	0.09
4841771	595695	2.0	3.1	3.7	10.5	1.4	5.8	1.2	0.39	1.5	0.19	1.13	0.22	0.65	0.09	0.56	0.08
4840192	594025	2.3	3.4	2.9	8.2	1.1	4.6	1.0	0.34	1.3	0.17	1.00	0.20	0.57	0.08	0.51	0.07
4840292	593218	2.0	3.5	2.6	7.2	1.0	4.1	0.9	0.31	1.1	0.15	0.89	0.18	0.51	0.07	0.45	0.07
4840700	590634	4.6	4.4	11.8	34.4	4.3	17.3	3.6	0.94	4.0	0.51	2.91	0.57	1.68	0.23	1.56	0.23
4840262	591043	2.0	3.2	3.0	8.6	1.2	4.9	1.1	0.36	1.3	0.17	1.01	0.20	0.59	0.08	0.53	0.08
4838254	590425	3.3	4.0	6.8	19.3	2.5	10.3	2.2	0.65	2.6	0.35	2.05	0.41	1.19	0.16	1.05	0.16
4837692	589949	4.9	4.6	14.6	42.5	5.2	20.7	4.2	1.03	4.6	0.58	3.23	0.63	1.82	0.24	1.60	0.24
4837259	590842	3.4	3.9	6.9	22.9	2.6	10.5	2.2	0.62	2.5	0.33	1.89	0.37	1.09	0.15	0.96	0.14
4839153	591219	2.3	3.0	2.1	7.0	0.9	3.7	0.8	0.28	1.0	0.13	0.79	0.15	0.42	0.05	0.33	0.05
4837158	591569	1.8	3.3	3.7	13.5	1.4	5.9	1.3	0.42	1.6	0.21	1.21	0.24	0.69	0.09	0.58	0.09
4836603	591576	1.0	2.1	2.8	8.0	1.0	4.5	1.0	0.31	1.2	0.16	0.93	0.18	0.53	0.07	0.44	0.06
4835706	590944	6.0	5.1	14.6	47.0	5.2	20.6	4.2	1.06	4.7	0.58	3.23	0.63	1.83	0.24	1.59	0.24
4835811	590539	4.3	4.0	10.6	30.3	3.8	15.3	3.2	0.90	3.7	0.48	2.76	0.54	1.57	0.20	1.35	0.20
4836845	593024	5.0	4.0	10.1	33.9	4.4	19.5	4.8	1.54	6.1	0.88	5.39	1.08	3.10	0.39	2.53	0.36
4835748	594007	5.8	5.3	15.8	46.2	5.6	21.9	4.4	1.11	4.9	0.60	3.35	0.65	1.90	0.25	1.67	0.25
4836037	590778	2.8	3.1	6.7	18.9	2.4	9.7	2.0	0.58	2.3							

Table 3. Total REE (ΣREE) and European Shale normalization average (or the range in its absence) for different surface sediment zones of Galician Rias and Shelf.

Zone	Sub-zone	Next to:	ΣREE	(La/Sm) _N	(Sm/Yb) _N	(La/Yb) _N	Reference
Cape Ortegal	Eastern Shelf	Ortegal Complex (eclogites & mafic)	44 ± 10	0.57 ± 0.09	0.57 ± 0.06**	0.32 ± 0.08*	This study
	Western Shelf	Ortegal Complex (ultramafic rock)	18 ± 5*	0.48 ± 0.01	0.64 ± 0.03	0.31 ± 0.01	
Mera River	Estuary (mud)	Ortegal Complex (Cariño gneiss)	115 ± 12*	0.71 ± 0.04	1.40 ± 0.13**	1.00 ± 0.14*	
Sor River	Estuary (mud)	Ollo-de-Sapo Domain	118 ± 10*	0.65 ± 0.03	1.19 ± 0.01	0.78 ± 0.05	
Ria of Ortigueira and Viveiro	Mouths and shelves	Ollo-de-Sapo Domain	51 ± 7	0.75 ± 0.12	1.12 ± 0.19	0.85 ± 0.15	
Landro River	Estuary (sand)	San-Ciprián Massifs	36 ± 12	0.84 ± 0.14	1.26 ± 0.31	1.04 ± 0.21*	
Ria of Barqueiro and Viveiro	Middle-outer parts	Barqueiro and San-Ciprián Massifs	45 ± 4	0.69 ± 0.12	1.08 ± 0.12	0.74 ± 0.12	
Cape Estaca de Bares	Shelf	Bares Massif	33 ± 10	0.74 ± 0.03	0.85 ± 0.09	0.63 ± 0.05	
Ria of Vigo	Inner part	Granites of Oitaven Basin	96 ± 39	1.13 ± 0.05	1.69 ± 0.17	1.92 ± 0.20	Prego et al., 2009
	Middle part	Galiñeiro Complex	188 ± 15	1.14 ± 0.22	1.66 ± 0.11	1.86 ± 0.49	
Miño River	Estuary	Malpica-Tuy Band	112 ± 49 ^(a)	1.06 ± 0.07	1.42 ± 0.26	1.54 ± 0.35	Gouveia et al., 1993
Western Galicia Shelf	Miño mud patch	Continental load	(143 – 305)	(0.84 – 1.06)	(0.99 – 1.23)	(0.94 – 1.30)	Araújo et al., 2007

^(a) Calculated without Pr, Gd, Dy, Ho, Er and Tm due to their concentrations were not indicated.

* significant at p < 0.05 level; ** significant at p < 0.01 level